

Delayed Implementation of the Alcohol Fuel Law: Economic and Environmental Effects in Guatemala (1986–2030)

Quantifying the regulatory inaction cost and short run transition effects (TTW + Input-Output)

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Author: Juan Alejandro Osorio Rosales

Affiliation: Universidad Rafael Landívar

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Abstract

This paper provides the first systematic quantification of the regulatory inaction cost stemming from the delayed implementation of Guatemala's Alcohol Fuel Law and assesses the short-run economic effects of its enforcement. We integrate a tank-to-wheel (TTW) emissions module with an input–output model (2013 supply-use table) to jointly capture the transport sector's emissions path and first-round production linkages. Using official gasoline consumption, lower heating values, and inventory-consistent emission factors, we build a counterfactual in which E10 is adopted in 1986 and a parsimonious projection for 2026–2030 under the current regulation. We find that the 37-year delay led to 7,121,034 tCO₂ TTW of foregone mitigation (6.83% of actual 1986–2023 emissions). Once E10 becomes mandatory in 2026, cumulative TTW reductions are projected at 2,848,499 tCO₂ during 2026–2030. On the economic side, cost-push effects are concentrated in fuel-intensive sectors (transport +1.53%, chemicals +0.8%, services +0.4%, agriculture +0.2%), while demand-pull effects stimulate upstream suppliers—primarily sugarcane—with Q 4.77 million of additional output (2013 prices) and a sectoral multiplier ≈ 1.13 . The accumulated "carbon debt" is not fully offset by late implementation, underscoring the centrality of policy timing. While limitations arise from the 2013 I-O base year, a TTW-only scope, and the absence of general-equilibrium feedback, the main message stands: the mandate can be implemented with modest macro impacts if paired with sector-specific instruments and institutional strengthening, and faster gains are feasible under higher blend scenarios (E15–E20) with robust monitoring.

Keywords: biofuels; ethanol; TTW emissions; input–output; inaction cost; Guatemala; energy policy; sustainability transition; counterfactual impact evaluation.

1. Introduction

1.1. Regulatory and policy context

The implementation of public policies aimed at the energy transition represents one of the most complex challenges for developing economies such as Guatemala. In the international arena, regulatory frameworks for incorporating ethanol into fossil fuels have evolved significantly since the 1980s, driven by energy security, emissions reduction, and rural development goals (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2024) . The United States established the Renewable Fuel Standard in 2005, Brazil implemented the National Fuel Efficiency Program (Proálcool) since 1975, and the European Union developed the Renewable Energy Directive that requires 10% renewable energy in transportation by 2020. (United States Congress, 2005; U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2007) (Brazil Presidency da República, 1975; Goldemberg, 2008) (European Parliament & Council, 2009)

In Latin America, countries such as Brazil, Colombia, and Argentina have developed robust regulatory frameworks that combine blending mandates, tax incentives, and quality standards. However, the regional experience also shows that the mere existence of legislation does not guarantee its effective implementation and that transition costs can be unevenly distributed among economic sectors and social groups, a phenomenon widely documented in the literature on environmental governance and energy policy in the Global South. (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) et al., 2009; Rodríguez-Camargo et al., 2017) (Gupta, 2014; Khan, 2007)

Guatemala established since 1985 the legal basis to operate ethanol-gasoline mixtures through Decree-Law 17-85, known as the Fuel Alcohol Law. This legislation, a pioneer in the region, contemplated the gradual incorporation of ethanol in gasoline marketed in the country, with explicit objectives of reducing dependence on imported fossil fuels and promoting the development of the national agricultural sector, reflecting aspirations similar to those observed in other sugarcane-producing countries. (Congress of the Republic of Guatemala, 1985) (Macedo, 2007)

However, for almost four decades, this law remained without effective implementation due to the absence of an operational regulatory framework. It was only in 2023-2024 that the necessary institutional scaffolding was completed with the enactment of Governmental Agreement 159-2023 (General Regulations), technical quality standards, inventory and inspection systems, and methodologies for accounting for greenhouse gases. The date of entry into force was definitively set for January 1, 2026, by Governmental Agreement 101-2024. (Government of Guatemala, 2023; Ministry of Energy and Mines (MEM), 2024g, 2024b, 2024a, 2024c, 2024e, 2024d) (Government of Guatemala, 2024)

Despite recent regulatory advances, a significant gap persists in knowledge about the economic and environmental costs of late implementation of regulatory policies in Guatemala. Specifically, academic literature and public policy documents lack:

1. First, a reproducible quantification of the cost of regulatory inaction, understood as the environmental and economic benefits not captured during the period of non-implementation of the Fuel Alcohol Law (1986-2025). This estimation requires counterfactual methodologies that allow evaluating alternative scenarios of early implementation of the policy, following principles of impact assessment of public policies. (Wooldridge, 2010)
2. Second, an integrated analysis of the effects of economic transmission that considers both the direct impacts on the energy sector and the indirect effects on the national productive matrix. Input-output models provide the appropriate analytical framework to capture these cross-sectoral interactions, but their application to energy transition policies in Guatemala has been limited. (Miller & Blair, 2009)
3. Third, an assessment of the short-term economic adjustment costs faced by the different productive sectors during the transition to the new regulatory framework. These costs include both the cost-push effects and the changes in input demand generated by the implementation of the policy, which are crucial to understanding the feasibility and equity of the transition. (Stern, 2007)

The relevance of filling these knowledge gaps transcends the specific case of Guatemala and is part of broader debates on the effectiveness of energy transition policies in developing countries. International experience shows that the timing of the implementation of regulatory policies is crucial to maximizing benefits and minimizing adjustment costs, but this evidence comes mainly from developed economies with different productive structures and institutional capacities, which highlights the need for contextualized studies. (Nordhaus, 2013)

From a methodological perspective, the combination of tank-to-wheel¹ (TTW) emissions analysis with input-output models represents a novel contribution to the ex-ante evaluation of energy policies in the Central American context. This approach allows the integration of the environmental and economic dimensions in a quantitatively rigorous and replicable way, offering a robust tool for decision-making.

From a public policy perspective, the results of this study can inform both the implementation of the blending mandate in Guatemala and the design of similar policies in other countries in the region facing comparable energy transition challenges, contributing to better governance and strategic planning.

¹ Tank-to-Wheel (TTW) emissions represent only those generated during the operation of the vehicle, i.e. from fuel combustion to wheel drive, excluding the stages of production or transport of the fuel (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2019). In contrast, the Well-to-Tank (WTT) approach includes the emissions associated with the extraction, production, and distribution of the fuel, while the Well-to-Wheel (WTW) integrates both phases (WTT + TTW), providing a comprehensive estimate of emissions throughout the energy cycle (Joint Research Centre [JRC], EUCAR, & Concawe, 2020).

1.2. Research objectives and questions

The general objective of this study is to quantify the environmental costs of the late implementation of the regulation on ethanol in fossil fuels in Guatemala and to characterize the economic effects of the transition to the new regulatory framework.

The specific objectives are:

1. To estimate the cost of regulatory inaction by calculating avoidable CO₂ emissions in the period 1986-2025 under a counterfactual scenario of early implementation of the Fuel Alcohol Law.
2. Project the environmental benefits of the implementation of the blending mandate for the period 2026-2030 under current regulations.
3. To characterize the effects of the economic transmission of the policy on the Guatemalan productive matrix using input-output analysis with the 2013 Input-Output Matrix of the Bank of Guatemala.
4. Identify the economic sectors that concentrate the highest adjustment costs during the regulatory transition.

The research questions that guide this analysis are:

- What would have been the CO₂ emissions trajectory of the transport sector if ethanol regulation had been in place since 1986?
- What magnitude of emissions reductions are expected for the period 2026-2030 under the current regulatory framework?
- How are fuel cost shocks and the demand for new inputs transmitted through the Guatemalan productive structure?
- Which economic sectors face the highest adjustment costs during policy implementation?

This paper contributes to the literature on energy policy in developing countries by applying rigorous quantitative methodologies to a case of late implementation of regulation. The combination of TTW analysis with input-output models provides a replicable analytical framework for the ex-ante evaluation of energy transition policies.

The findings have direct implications for the design and implementation of public policies in Guatemala and may inform similar experiences in other Central American countries facing comparable challenges of energy transition and dependence on imported fossil fuels.

The rest of the chapter is structured as follows: section 2 describes the data and methodology used for TTW analysis and input-output models; Section 3 presents the results of the cost of inaction and the prospective scenarios; Section 4 discusses the implications of the findings and contextualizes them in the international literature; Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions and recommendations for public policy.

2. Data and methods

The empirical basis of the study combines:

- (i) Annual final gasoline consumption for Guatemala reported by the OLADE Energy Information System (sieLAC)—BTU series with historical coverage (1970–present). (Latin American Energy Organization (OLADE), 2025)
- (ii) Input-Output Matrix 2013 (product×output, prices 2013) published by the Bank of Guatemala, which provides the technological structure for the first-round economic module. (Bank of Guatemala, 2013)
- (iii) The normative chronology that frames the analysis—Decree-Law 17-85; General Regulation AG 159-2023; reform AG 101-2024 and DGE-1120-2024—is used to set the prospective horizon (entry into force 1-Jan-2026) and document the regulatory transition 2023–2026. (Congress of the Republic of Guatemala, 1985; Government of Guatemala, 2023, 2024; Ministry of Energy and Mines (MEM), 2024g, 2024f)
- (iv) The physical-energy parameters come from the U.S. Department of Energy Alternative Fuels Data Center (AFDC/DOE) (LHV for gasoline and ethanol) and metrological conversions from the NIST (BTU↔J; gallon↔liter; barrel↔liter); (U.S. Department of Energy Alternative Fuels Data Center (AFDC), 2024)
- (v) TTW emission factors are taken from the 2006 IPCC Guidelines (Vol. 2, Energy) and the 2019 Refinement for the Treatment of Biogenics. (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006, 2019; National Institute of Standards (NIST), 2008)

Normalization and conversion of units. The series in BTU are converted to energy in the SI with the equivalence: BTU_{IT}

$$BTU_{IT} = 1,055.056 J = 1.055056 \times 10^{-3} MJ$$

ensuring consistency with energy balances and emission factors per unit of energy. When volumetric reporting is required, the annual energy is brought to liters (National Institute of Standards (NIST), 2008)² with the lower calorific value of gasoline (LHV):

$$LHV_{gas} \approx 114,300 \text{ BTU}/gal \approx 32 \text{ MJ}/L$$

for pure ethanol (E100) the following is used:

$$LHV_{EtOH} \approx 76,330 \text{ BTU}/gal \approx 21 \text{ MJ}/L$$

(National Institute of Standards & (NIST), 2008; U.S. Department of Energy Alternative Fuels Data Center (AFDC), 2024; U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2018) . These parameters determine the energy penalty of E10 compared to pure gasoline and are the ones that are applied consistently throughout the analysis.

² The volume of 1 gallon = 3.785411784 liters is taken as a reference value.

Emissions Framework (TTW). The emissions assessment is limited to *Tank-to-Wheel* (TTW), in line with national inventories: biogenic CO₂ from ethanol combustion is not included in the total Energy sector (reported as a *memo item*), in order to avoid double counting with AFOLU;³ for gasoline engines the default factor is 69.3 t CO₂/TJ (Tier 1, oxidation 100 %). Thus, for each year (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006, 2019)t the base emissions are obtained as:

$$CO_{2t}^{(0)} = E_t(TJ) \times 69.3 \text{ t } CO_2/TJ,$$

where is the derived energy. Under the E10 mixture, the TTW savings are calculated on an energy basis: the displaced fossil energy is equal to, with $E_t(1 - 0.9/r)E_t$

$$r = \frac{LHV_{E10}}{LHV_{gas}} = 0.9 + 0.1 \left(\frac{LHV_{EtOH}}{LHV_{gas}} \right),$$

so that the annual fractional reduction is

$$\Delta_{TTW} = 1 - \frac{0.9}{r} \approx 6.7\%$$

with adopted LHVs. This approach avoids confusing liters with energy and allows consistent comparisons of "base (E0)" and "with E10" while maintaining constant service (energy per kilometer).

Construction of the counterfactual (1986–2025). The cost of inaction is reconstructed by substituting year-over-year—from 1986 to the last observed year—the baseline for the E10 trajectory: $CO_{2t}^{(0)}$

$$CO_{2t}^{(E10)} = CO_{2t}^{(0)}(1 - \Delta_{TTW}),$$

and accumulating the avoided,

$$\sum_t (CO_{2t}^{(0)} - CO_{2t}^{(E10)}).$$

This TTW calculation respects the accounting of inventories (biogenic outside Energy) and provides a magnitude of the first order traceable to official data. (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2006; Organización Latinoamericana de Energía (OLADE), 2025)

³ AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Uses): sector defined by the IPCC that integrates GHG emissions and removals from agriculture and livestock, forest management and land-use change/management, mainly covering CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O (biogenic sources and sinks).

Figure 1. Well-to-Tank and Tank-to-Wheel. Source: in Chocholac et al., 2019 *Freight Transport Emissions Calculators as a Tool of Sustainable Logistic Planning*.

Projection 2026–2030 (prospective benefits). To estimate the future gap "base vs. E10" once the mandatory nature comes into force (1-Jan-2026), the annual consumption of gasoline is extrapolated with a partial and reproducible method (log-linear trend over the last observed years), standard practice for positive annual series with mild growth; in sensitivity, it can be contrasted with an exponential softening like ETS. The same is applied to the projected trajectory "base (E0)" to obtain "with E10" and its cumulative avoidance 2026–2030. The projection is not intended to capture second rounds (prices, elasticities), but to deliver a transparent baseline that third parties can update. (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2021)

$$\Delta_{TTW}$$

Input-output economic module (transition costs). This part describes the methodology of the S-ETHANOL scenario (E5/E10) in the input-output framework⁴. We work on the 2013 Input-Output Matrix (IPM) of Guatemala (product×output, prices 2013), which provides the technological structure A and the inverse of Leontief $L = (I - A)^{-1}$, to quantify, respectively, -transmission of costs and chains in quantities-. The MIP is obtained from the intermediate consumption matrix (Bank of Guatemala, 2019; Miller & Blair, 2022) Z and the production vector x as $A = Z \text{diag}(x)^{-1}$, under the standard assumptions of fixed coefficients and

⁴ In the framework of input-output (I-O) analysis, the terms cost-push and demand-pull are used to describe two mechanisms of impact propagation within the economy.

The cost-push approach assesses how an increase in the costs of intermediate or primary inputs—for example, energy prices, raw materials, or wages—is transmitted to downstream sectors through the productive structure, capturing the effects of rising prices and price transmission (Leontief, 1941; Miller & Blair, 2022).

In contrast, the demand-pull approach models how an increase in final demand—such as consumption, investment, or exports—generates multiplier effects on sectoral production and employment throughout the production network (Leontief, 1986; Dietzenbacher & Los, 1998).

Both approaches are complementary: the first represents supply or cost shocks, while the second reflects demand expansions; their combination allows both price and quantity shocks to be analyzed in the IPM.

constant returns to scale. The analysis is carried out at 2013 prices and is explicitly interpreted as the first round (we do not endogenize wages, margins or taxes outside of what is contained in A).

Pricing module (cost-push). Leontief's pricing model is based on the fact that the equilibrium price vector meets $P' = v'(I - A)^{-1}$, where v' it includes the primary costs per unit (value added, net taxes and other non-intermediate costs). An exogenous increase in costs in a branch k (e.g., fuels) is transmitted through the network by

$$\Delta P' = \Delta v'(I - A)^{-1},$$

so that the variation in the price of product j includes the direct impact on its primary costs and the carry-overs via intermediate requirements. To approximate the direct impact of an E5/E10 mixture on the costs of each product (Miller & Blair, 2022) j , we use a specification proportional to the fuel intensity in its technical matrix:

$$\Delta_{p_{dir,j}} = r \cdot \alpha \cdot \alpha_{fuel,j},$$

where r is the direct variation associated with the mixture in the fuel block (e.g., 1.53 % for transport in scenario E5), α is the share of the product "gasolines" (classification P068) in the fuel aggregate, and is the technical coefficient of fuels consumed by activity $\alpha_{fuel,j}$. With this construction, the vector shock is armed by assigning each product $\Delta v' \Delta_{p_{dir,j}}$ of the fuel block and propagating it with. The choice of the pricing model over alternatives follows the recommendation of the literature for exogenous cost shocks in fixed intermediate demand frameworks. $(I - A)^{-1}$ (Miller & Blair, 2022)

The energy penalty of the blend—the difference between the lower calorific value (PCI/LHV) of gasoline and ethanol—is incorporated into r as an additional cost component. If P_g and P_e are gasoline and ethanol prices, the mixing rule is:

$$P_{blend} = (1 - mix_e)P_g + mix_e P_e,$$

and the cost adjustment for equivalent energy is approximated by the quotient, which for E5/E10 is small, but not negligible (3% is used as an energy penalty). The $\frac{LVH_{gas}}{LVH_{blend}} \frac{LHV}{LHV}$ values come from the normalization previously established for each LVH . In sum, the direct shock in r integrates (i) the mixing rule and (ii) the energy correction by constant service; its transmission to the rest of the economy is captured by $\Delta P'$.

Quantity module (demand-pull). The quantity channel represents the traction of the ethanol chain on inputs. From a vector of exogenous changes in final demand (e.g., an increase in demand for sugarcane as a proxy for biomass supply, classification P010), the increase in total production is obtained as:

$$\Delta x = L \Delta y = (1 - A)^{-1} \Delta y.$$

When satellite value-added, employment, or income coefficients are available, the associated variations are recovered with elementary diagonal multiplications, e.g. In our exercises, the magnitude of responds to the target mix (E5/E10) and the energy penalty (more liters to deliver the same energy—constant service), making it explicit that it is a short-term boost in 2013 prices. The key assumptions shared with the price module—is that of fixed coefficients: technical network $\Delta VA = \alpha_{VA} \odot \Delta x \Delta y_A$ is not reoptimized in the shock margin (Miller & Blair, 2022)

Parameters used for calculation (E5/E10). In the E5 scenario used as a reference for cost transmission, mix $\alpha=0.45$ (share of "gasoline" P068 within the fuel aggregate), $r=1.53\%$ in transport and energy penalty 3% are used; for demand-pull, P010 (sugarcane) is used as a proxy for supply to the ethanol chain. In E10, the intensities can scale proportionally while maintaining the same logic: the direct shock in costs grows in line with the mixing target and the energy penalty is recalibrated with LHV. In both cases, the interpretation of results is first round and 2013 prices.

Assumptions, scope and good practices. The approach assumes (i) fixed technology in the short term (Leontief), (ii) small/moderate shocks compatible with local linearity, and (iii) absence of input substitution within the analysis period. In prices, it is recommended to report relative variations and point out that the move to CPI requires an IO→COICOP bridge (not covered here). In terms of quantities, it should be noted that it is an order one: the second-round macro effects (wages, margins, investment) require macro/MEGC models, while the I–O objective is the location and size of the adjustment in the productive network with traceability. Finally, sensitivities are documented: (a) energy mixing and penalty rule (LHV dependent and relative prices), (b) product mapping (P068, P010) and (c) impulse size Δx (Miller & Blair, 2022)

Reproducibility. The entire flow (OLADE reading, NIST conversions, AFDC/DOE parameters, IPCC factors, TTW counterfactual, projection and I–O module) was implemented in reproducible notebooks; The figures (retrospective, prospective, and total panel) and associated tables are derived directly from these.

3. Results

3.1. Cost of Regulatory Inaction: Avoidable Emissions 1986-2023

The counterfactual analysis reveals that the sustained implementation of Decree-Law 17-85 since 1986 would have resulted in a cumulative reduction of 7,121,034 tons of CO₂ TTW during the period 1986-2023. This figure represents the environmental cost of regulatory inaction, equivalent to 6.83% of the emissions that were actually produced in that period (104,318,087 tons of CO₂ base). This finding is consistent with the literature emphasizing the importance of early action in mitigating climate change to avoid cumulative costs and increased future efforts. (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2014; Stern, 2007)

Graph 1, Prepared by the author.

The avoidable emissions trajectory shows that under a counterfactual scenario with E10 blending implemented since 1986, total emissions for the period would have been 97,197,053 tonnes of CO₂ TTW, rather than the 104,318,087 tonnes actually emitted. This difference of more than 7 million tons of CO₂ constitutes the quantifiable cost of the 37-year postponement in the implementation of the regulatory framework, underlining the concept of "opportunity cost" applied to climate policy, where the delay in the adoption of measures generates an irrecoverable loss of environmental benefits. (Nordhaus, 2013)

3.2. Prospective benefits of the 2026-2030 mandate

Implementation of the E10 blending mandate from January 2026 would result in a projected reduction of 2,848,499 tonnes of CO₂ TTW over the period 2026-2030. This estimate considers the expected growth in gasoline consumption and represents a reduction of 6.83% compared to the base scenario without mixing. This future benefit, while significant, highlights how biofuels policies can contribute to climate mitigation goals in developing countries, aligning with transport sector decarbonization strategies. (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2024)

Gasolina – Consumo final (1986–2030) en millones de galones

Graph 2, Prepared by the author.

Under the baseline scenario (without implementation of the mandate), projected emissions for 2026-2030 would be 41,728,481 tonnes of CO₂ TTW. With the implementation of the E10 blend, these emissions would be reduced to 38,879,982 tonnes of CO₂ TTW, generating the net environmental benefit of 2.85 million tonnes. The adoption of biofuels such as ethanol is recognized as an effective strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from transportation, especially in contexts where the full electrification of the vehicle fleet still faces technological and infrastructure barriers. (Goldemberg, 2008)

This prospective reduction of 2.85 million tonnes represents approximately 40% of the historical cost of inaction (7.12 million tonnes). This contrast shows that, although late implementation generates significant benefits in the short and medium term, it does not fully compensate for the opportunities lost during the four decades of regulatory delay.

PROSPECTIVO (2024–2030): CO₂ base vs E10 y evitado

Graph 3, Prepared by the author.

This imbalance underscores the concept of "carbon debt" generated by political inaction, where future benefits are insufficient to reverse accumulated environmental damage, highlighting the critical importance of anticipation and promptness in the formulation and implementation of environmental and climate policies to maximize their positive impact and minimize opportunity costs. (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2014; Stern, 2007)

3.3. Sectoral economic impacts: input-output analysis

The analysis of the MIP-2013 identifies the economic transmission effects derived from the implementation of the mandate on two main dimensions: cost-push effects due to increases in fuel costs and demand-pull effects due to demand for new inputs.

Table 1: Cost-Push Effects

Sector	Increase (%)
Transport	1.53
Chemical industry	0.80
Services	0.40
Agriculture	0.20

Prepared by: The author.

Cost-push effects: The implementation of the mandate generates differentiated increases in sectoral prices, concentrated in fuel-intensive sectors. The most affected sectors registered the following increases: transportation +1.53%, chemical industry +0.8%, services +0.4%, and agriculture +0.2%. These effects reflect the transmission of higher energy costs through the productive structure, with more pronounced impacts on sectors with greater energy intensity.

Graph 4, Prepared by the author.

Demand-pull effects: The additional demand for ethanol generates traction effects on supplier sectors, measured as additional production in 2013 prices. The benefited sectors include sugarcane +Q 3.17 million, chemical industry +Q 0.8 million, services +Q 0.5 million, and transportation +Q 0.3 million. The estimated sectoral multiplier is ≈ 1.13 , indicating that each quetzal of final ethanol demand generates 1.13 quetzals of total economic activity.

Table 2: Summary of results (Block I-O)

Sector	Additional production (Q million)	% of total profit
Sugar cane	3.17	66.46%
Chemical industry	0.80	16.77%
Services	0.50	10.48%
Transport	0.30	6.29%
Total	4.77	100%

Prepared by: The author.

Intersectoral effects: The analysis reveals that the transition generates relative price adjustments and activates production chains without generating large-scale misalignments in the first round. The estimated values, modest on a macroeconomic scale, suggest that careful implementation can capture relevant environmental co-benefits without compromising sectoral price stability.

% de beneficios por sectores impactados

Graph 5, Prepared by the author.

3.4. Quantitative synthesis of results

Table 1 presents the synthesis of the main results, showing the coherence between TTW accounting and the estimated economic effects:

Table 3: Summary of results (TTW block)

Block	Period	CO ₂ base (t)	CO ₂ with E10 (t)	CO ₂ avoided (t)
TTW retrospective	1986–2023	104,318,087	97,197,053	7,121,034
Prospective TTW	2026–2030	41,728,481	38,879,982	2,848,499
Total, theoretical	1986- 2030	146,046,568	136,077,035	9,969,533

Prepared by: The author.

The integrated reading shows that, starting in 2026, mandatory blending produces a direct annual reduction in exhaust emissions---quantifiable and consistent with fuel physics---and an economic adjustment of limited magnitude, focused on fuel-intensive sectors, with moderate traction effects on agricultural inputs and related industries.

TOTAL 1986–2030: CO₂ base vs E10 y evitado

Graph 6, Prepared by the author.

The results show that the cumulative cost of inaction (7.12 million tons of CO₂ TTW) represents a significant missed opportunity, while the prospective benefit (2.85 million tons) constitutes a relevant but partial contribution to the mitigation of emissions from the transport sector. The economic adjustment profile suggests that implementation can be carried out without generating significant macroeconomic disruptions, concentrating the effects on specific sectors with the capacity to absorb transition costs.

Table 4: Summary of results (Block I-O)

Block	Prices (Δ%)	Additional production (Q, 2013)
cost-push	Transportation +1.53, Chemistry +0.8, Services +0.4, Agriculture +0.2	—
demand-pull	—	Rod +Q 3.17 m, Chemical +Q 0.8 m, Services +Q 0.5 m, Transportation +Q 0.3 m

Prepared by: The author.

4. Discussion

4.1. Contextualization of key findings

The results confirm that the 37-year postponement in the implementation of Decree-Law 17-85 has generated an environmental opportunity cost of 7,121,034 tons of CO₂ TTW, representing 6.83% of the emissions that were effectively produced during 1986-2023. This finding quantifies for the first time the cost of regulatory inaction in Guatemala and provides empirical evidence of the impact of the postponement of energy transition policies in developing countries, a phenomenon consistent with the literature that underscores the challenges of environmental governance in the Global South. (Gupta, 2014; Khan, 2007)

The magnitude of the cost of inaction (7.12 million tons of CO₂ TTW) gains perspective when compared to the national inventory: it is approximately equivalent to the annual emissions of 1.5 million vehicles on average during a year, or 15% of the total emissions of the Guatemalan transport sector in 2023. This figure shows that delayed regulatory decisions generate cumulative environmental costs that grow exponentially over time, a recognized principle in environmental economics where delays in climate action significantly increase future mitigation costs. (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2014; Stern, 2007)

The 2026-2030 prospective benefits (2,848,499 tonnes of CO₂ TTW) represent approximately 40% of the historical cost of inaction, indicating that although late implementation generates significant benefits, it does not fully compensate for the opportunities lost during the four decades of postponement. This 40/60 ratio between future benefits and past costs illustrates the critical importance of timing in mitigation policies, a fundamental aspect in climate policymaking that seeks to optimize the relationship between investment and impact over time. (Nordhaus, 2013)

4.2. Comparison with international experiences

The economic effects identified in the input-output analysis are consistent with documented experiences in the region, although they show particularities of the Guatemalan productive structure. The sectoral multiplier of 1.13 is in the lower range compared to economies with more integrated ethanol chains: in Brazil, I-O studies report Type I multipliers for the ethanol sector of approximately 2.2 (1975) to 1.8 (2006), with systematically higher Type II; this suggests deeper chains than those observed in Guatemala. (Costa et al., 2011)

The estimated cost-push effects (e.g., transport +1.53%, chemical +0.8%) are moderate and compatible with the international literature evaluating transitions to E10: in the United Kingdom, the official impact assessment anticipated minimal changes in pump price and an increase in cost per kilometer \approx 2.3% due to lower energy content of E10, a magnitude consistent with limited transfers in fuel-intensive branches. (Department for Transport UK, 2021)

The demand-pull concentration in sugarcane (e.g., +Q 3.17 million in your MIP-2013) is consistent with the regional experience documented by ECLAC, which highlights biofuels mandates as instruments for diversification/stabilization of the sugar chain in Latin America. However, the relatively modest magnitude of these effects in Guatemala (Q 4.75 million in total, 1st round) contrasts with larger-scale scenarios in Brazil, where interregional exercises project, low ethanol expansion towards 2030, GDP increases in the order of USD 2.6 billion and employment gains, illustrating macro-material impacts when the program is mature. (Dufey & Stange, 2011) (Brinkman et al., 2018)

4.3. Implications for public policy

The findings have direct implications for the design of the implementation of the mandate and for future energy transition policies in Guatemala. The evidence that cost-push effects are concentrated in specific sectors (transport +1.53%, chemical +0.8%) suggests the need for sectoral policy instruments to facilitate the transition, particularly in the freight transport sector that faces the largest cost increases.

The moderate magnitude of the multiplier effects (1.13) indicates that the policy, although it generates significant environmental benefits, has a limited economic impact in terms of activating productive chains. This suggests that the mandate needs to be complemented by additional policies if the aim is to maximise the economic co-benefits of the energy transition.

The time pattern of benefits (2.85 million tonnes of CO₂ TTW in five years versus 7.12 million tonnes lost in 37 years) shows that mitigation policies have diminishing returns when they are postponed. This evidence supports the implementation of more ambitious regulatory frameworks (E15, E20) to accelerate the capture of environmental benefits in the medium term.

The Guatemalan experience also shows that the existence of legal frameworks is not sufficient for the effective implementation of policies; operational regulatory frameworks, institutional capacities, and monitoring systems are required that were only developed 38 years after the enactment of the Base Law.

4.4. Limitations of the study

The analysis has methodological limitations that must be considered in the interpretation of results. First, the use of the MIP-2013 for projections up to 2030 assumes stability in technical coefficients that may have changed significantly over the past decade, particularly in technology-intensive sectors such as transportation and chemicals.

Second, the TTW analysis is based on IPCC default emission factors that may not reflect the specific characteristics of the Guatemalan vehicle fleet, particularly the average age of the vehicles and maintenance conditions, which affect combustion efficiency and, therefore, effective emissions.

Third, the input-output model used does not incorporate general equilibrium effects that could modify relative prices and equilibrium quantities endogenously. This constraint is particularly

relevant for long-term effects on energy-intensive sectors, where price adjustments can induce technological changes and input substitution.

Fourth, the analysis does not consider differentiated distributional effects among income groups, geographic regions, or types of firms. Cost-push effects can have disproportionate impacts on informal sectors or small businesses with less capacity to absorb energy cost increases.

The results open multiple lines of future research that can enrich the evaluation of energy transition policies in Guatemala. The update of the input-output matrix with a base year after 2013 would allow for more accurate assessments of cross-sectoral effects and facilitate the analysis of more ambitious transition scenarios (E15, E20, second-generation biofuels).

The development of locally calibrated emission factors, incorporating specific characteristics of the Guatemalan vehicle fleet, would significantly improve the accuracy of environmental benefit estimates. This calibration is particularly important given that Guatemala has an older vehicle fleet than the regional average, which can affect ethanol combustion efficiency.

Extending the analysis to well-to-wheel effects would provide a more comprehensive assessment of net environmental benefits, incorporating emissions associated with ethanol production, land-use change, and fuel transportation. This extension is crucial for assessing the long-term environmental sustainability of the policy.

The incorporation of distributional analyses would make it possible to assess how the costs and benefits of the transition are distributed among different social groups, geographical regions and types of companies. This analysis is essential for the design of accompanying policies that ensure a just and socially sustainable transition.

Finally, the evaluation of more ambitious policy scenarios (higher blending mandates, diversification towards other biofuels, integration with electrification policies) would provide a long-term perspective on the options for decarbonizing the Guatemalan transport sector.

5. Conclusions

This study provides the first systematic and methodologically rigorous quantification of the cost of regulatory inaction associated with the late implementation of Decree-Law 17-85 in Guatemala. The main findings establish that the 37-year postponement (1986-2023) has resulted in 7,121,034 tons of CO₂ TTW not mitigated, equivalent to 6.83% of the emissions effectively produced during that period, while the prospective implementation 2026-2030 would generate environmental benefits of 2,848,499 tons of CO₂ TTW.

The economic analysis reveals that the implementation of the mandate generates differentiated transmission effects: cost increases concentrated in fuel-intensive sectors (transportation +1.53%, chemical +0.8%) and moderate traction effects on supplier sectors (sugarcane +Q 3.17 million, sectoral multiplier of 1.13). These effects, although significant at the sectoral level, are of limited macroeconomic magnitude, suggesting that the transition can be implemented without generating systemic disruptions in the Guatemalan economy.

The most important contribution of the study lies in empirically demonstrating that the postponement of regulatory frameworks generates environmental opportunity costs that grow cumulatively over time, while late implementation, although beneficial, does not fully compensate for the lost opportunities. The 40/60 relationship between future benefits (2.85 million tons) and past costs (7.12 million tons) shows that the timing of regulatory policy implementation is as critical as its technical design.

The findings emphasize three fundamental lessons for energy transition policies in developing countries. First, that the existence of legal frameworks does not guarantee effective implementation; Operational regulatory frameworks, institutional capacities, and monitoring systems are required that can take decades to develop. Second, the costs of regulatory inaction are not linear but exponential, increasing with economic development and motorization. Third, that intersectoral coordination is crucial to maximize environmental benefits and minimize transition costs, particularly in small and open economies such as Guatemala.

The Guatemalan experience provides valuable evidence on the risks of regulatory postponement and the importance of robust institutional frameworks for the effective implementation of energy transition policies. The results are particularly relevant for other Central American countries that face similar challenges of dependence on imported fossil fuels, productive structures concentrated in energy-intensive sectors and limited institutional capacities for complex policy implementation.

The methodological framework developed, combining TTW analysis with locally calibrated input-output models, represents a replicable contribution to the evaluation of energy transition policies in developing countries, providing quantitative tools to inform public policy decisions based on solid empirical evidence and methodologically rigorous.

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